

Online Supplement

Global knockout of melanoma differentiation-associated protein 5 protects mice from chronic hypoxia/SU5416-induced pulmonary hypertension

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SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS AND METHODS

Key reagents

Antibodies: MDA5 (Cat. No. LS-A10978, LS Bio, Newark, CA, dilution 1:200), MDA5 (Cat. No. 5321, Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, MA, dilution 1:1000), α -smooth muscle actin (α -SMA, Cat. No. M0851, Agilent DAKO, Santa Clara, CA, dilution 1:100), β -actin (Cat. No. A5441, Millipore Sigma, Burlington, MA, dilution 1:5000), anti-rabbit AF488-linked antibody (Cat. No. AF21441, Invitrogen, Waltham, MA, dilution 1:20), anti-mouse IgG_{2a} AF647-linked antibody (Cat. No. AF21241, Invitrogen, dilution 1:20), anti-mouse HRP-linked antibody (Cat. No. 7076, Cell Signaling Technology, dilution 1:1000), anti-rabbit HRP-linked antibody (Cat. No. 7074, Cell Signaling Technology, dilution 1:1000), CD11b (Cat. No. NB110-89474, Novus Biologicals, Centennial, CO, dilution 1:1000), CD4 (Cat. No. ab125711, Abcam, dilution 1:50).

Other reagents: Texas Red-conjugated Tomatolactin (*Lycopersicon Esculentum* lectin) (Cat. No. TL-1176-1, Vector Biolabs, Malvern, PA, dilution 1:50), 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI, Cat. No. D1306, Invitrogen, dilution 1:5000), SU5416 (Cat. No. S8442, Millipore Sigma), RIPA buffer (Cat. No. R0278, Millipore Sigma), Protease inhibitor cocktail (Cat. No. A32955, ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA), Phosphatase inhibitor cocktail (Cat. No. P2850, Millipore Sigma), nitrocellulose membrane (Cat. No. 1620094, BioRad, Hercules, CA), SlowFade Gold (Cat. No. S36936, ThermoFisher), BD APC BrdU Flow kit (BD Pharmingen, Cat. No. 51-9000019AK), non-targeting control siRNA (464945667 51-01-14-04, Integrated DNA Technologies, IDT, Newark, NJ), human MDA5 gene (*IFIH1*)-targeting siRNA (Cat. No. 464945664 hs.Ri.IFIH1.13.2, IDT), GeneMute transfection reagent (Cat. No. SL100568, SignaGen Laboratories, Frederick,

MD), growth factor-reduced Matrigel (Cat. No. CLS354230, Corning, Corning, NY), iTaq SYBR Green Master Mix (Cat. No. 1725120, Bio-Rad).

Cell culture experiments

Human pulmonary artery endothelial cells (PAECs) and pulmonary artery smooth muscle cells (PASMCs) were obtained in a de-identified manner from the Pulmonary Hypertension Breakthrough Initiative (PHBI) and UC Davis. The PAECs used in this study were level III PAECs as per the definition of the Pulmonary Hypertension Breakthrough Initiative, with a diameter < 1mm, representing PAECs close to microvascular PAECs. We posit that these PAECs better correspond than lung microvascular ECs, which contain capillary ECs, to the small precapillary pulmonary arterioles, which are predominantly affected by the pathobiological changes (1). Control PAECs were obtained from failed donor lungs and isolated in the same way as the PAH samples. For cell line authentication, cell type-specific morphology (PAEC: cobblestone morphology, PASMC: hill-and-valley morphology) was regularly observed by microscopy, and verified using cell-specific functional assays and/or by staining for cell-type-specific markers. In case of uncertain cell identity, cell lines were not used or verified by short tandem repeat profiling. Mycoplasma testing was performed regularly using the MycoStrip assay (Cat. No. rep-mys-10, Invivogen, San Diego, CA, USA), and only cell cultures with negative results were used in the experiments. The PAECs were cultured in endothelial growth medium MV2 (Promocell, Heidelberg, Germany, Cat. No. C-22022) in a humidified incubator at 5% CO₂. PASMCs were cultured in smooth muscle cell growth medium (Lonza, Walkersville, MD, Cat. No. CC-3182). Immortalized human PASMCs were obtained from

Applied Biological Materials, Richmond, BC, Canada (T0558) and cultured in complete PriGrow II Medium (Cat. No. TM002, Applied Biological Materials), supplemented with 5% FBS and 1% Penicillin/Streptomycin Solution, at 37.0°C and 5% CO₂ in a humidified incubator using rat tail type I collagen-coated cell culture vessels and dishes. Human macrophage-like cells were differentiated from THP-1 cells (American Type Cell Culture Collection, ATCC, Manassas, VA, Cat. No. TIB-202, RRID:CVCL_0006) using 20 ng/ml Phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA, Cat. No. tlr1-pma, Invivogen, San Diego, CA) for 72h before siRNA treatment in RPMI 1640 supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% Penicillin/Streptomycin. For siRNA transfection, non-targeting control siRNA (Cat. No. 464945667 51-01-14-04, Integrated DNA Technologies, IDT, Newark, NJ) and human MDA5 gene (*IFIH1*)-targeting siRNA (Cat. No. 464945664 hs.Ri.IFIH1.13.2, IDT) were transfected at 50 nM using GeneMute transfection reagent (Cat. No. SL100568, SignaGen Laboratories, Frederick, MD). THP-1 cells received nucleic acid transfection & transduction enhancer (NATE, Cat. No. lyec-nate, Invivogen) 30 min before adding siRNA according to the manufacturer's instruction. After 16 hours, the cell culture medium was changed for PAECs and PSMCs, and experiments were performed 48 or 72 hours after transfection.

Cell cycle analysis was performed using a commercial kit (BD APC BrdU Flow kit, BD Pharmingen, Cat. No. 51-9000019AK). In brief, 72 hours after transfection, cells were pulsed with 5-bromodeoxyuridine (BrdU, 10 µM) for 4 hours, after which the cells were removed from the cell culture dishes for flow cytometry staining. The cells were fixed and permeabilized, then treated with DNase and incubated with an APC-linked anti-BrdU antibody. DNA was stained with 7-aminoactinomycin D (7-AAD). Analysis was conducted

with a BD FACSSymphony A1 flow cytometer (BD Biosciences) and FlowJo Software (FlowJo, LLC, Ashland, OR).

To analyze angiogenic network formation, a 2D Matrigel network formation assay was used as previously published (2, 3). In brief, following transfection with siRNA, PAECs were seeded in Ibidi μ -Slide for angiogenesis (Cat. No. 81506, Ibidi, Gräfelfing, Germany) on growth factor-reduced Matrigel (Cat. No. CLS354230, Corning, Corning, NY). After 20 hours, image acquisition was conducted with an inverted automated EVOS M7000 microscope (ThermoFisher, Cincinnati, OH) (4x objective). The microscopy images for control and MDA5 siRNA were acquired simultaneously under the same conditions. Network formation was quantified in a blinded manner using Angiotool software (National Cancer Institute) (4).

To determine the migration capacity, a gap closure assay was performed. ECs were seeded in 3-well migration assay culture inserts (Ibidi, Cat. No. 80369). In confluent cell layers, a well-defined uniform gap was generated by removing the insert (t=0 hours), and gap closure was observed after 16 hours, as described previously (3). Images were acquired using an inverted automated EVOS M7000 microscope (ThermoFisher) (4x objective). The microscopy images for control and MDA5 siRNA were acquired simultaneously under the same conditions. The gap area was measured in a blinded manner at 0 hours (A_{0h}) and 16 hours (A_{16h}) using Fiji software (5). The gap closure (%) was quantified as $(A_{0h}-A_{16h})/(A_{0h})\times 100\%$

Histology

Tissue sources

De-identified lung tissue sections of formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded lung tissue from control and PAH patients were obtained from the PHBI. Control lung tissues were obtained from failed donor lungs and isolated in the same way as the PAH samples. For mouse histology, the left lung was inflated at a pressure of 20 cmH₂O with 10% neutral-buffered formalin, followed by immersion in 10% formalin for 24h. Then, transversal sections were processed and paraffin-embedded by Histowiz (Long Island City, NY).

Immunohistochemistry

For immunohistochemistry, tissue sections were rehydrated and then subjected to antigen retrieval by heating in boiling citrate buffer (pH 6.0) for 20 minutes. H₂O₂ was used to block endogenous peroxidase, followed by blocking of non-specific binding with 1% normal swine serum (NSS) in PBS for 15 minutes. The sections were then incubated overnight at 4°C with the primary antibody diluted in 1% NSS/PBS. The following day, slides were incubated for 1 hour with a biotin-labeled secondary antibody diluted in 1% NSS/PBS. This was followed by a 1-hour incubation with horse radish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated streptavidin. Detection was performed using diaminobenzidine (DAB) substrate, and slides were counterstained with Mayer's hematoxylin. Lastly, the slides were dehydrated and mounted using coverslips and a permanent mounting medium.

Immunofluorescence and confocal microscopy

Immunofluorescence was performed as published previously (3) after rehydration and included antigen retrieval (20 minutes of heating in boiling citrate buffer pH 6.0). Blocking of nonspecific binding was done with 1% normal swine serum (NSS)/PBS for 15 minutes. Primary antibody #1 was incubated in 1% NSS/PBS overnight at 4°C. Then, a secondary fluorescence-labeled antibody was applied for 4 hours (diluted in 1% NSS/PBS), followed by incubation with primary antibody #2 overnight at 4°C. A second incubation with secondary fluorescence-labeled antibody #2 was performed for 4 hours. Additionally, samples were incubated overnight with Tomato lectin, followed by nuclear staining with DAPI for 5 minutes. Finally, the sections were mounted with coverslips using SlowFade Gold (ThermoFisher, S36936).

Optical sections of immunofluorescence were captured using an inverted Olympus FV3000 confocal microscope system at the OSU Campus Microscopy and Imaging Facility. The microscopy images for control and PAH patients were acquired simultaneously under the same conditions. The images were assembled using Fiji software (5).

Quantification

Media wall thickness (MWT) was analyzed as described previously (3). In brief, analysis was performed on images of pulmonary arteries (H&E staining) acquired by Histowiz. The microscopy images for MDA5^{-/-} and MDA5^{+/+} mice were acquired simultaneously under the same conditions. Treatment groups were masked by numerical coding. The pulmonary arteries were randomly selected and analyzed in a blinded

manner. After measurement of media thickness (MT) and external diameter (ED), MWT was calculated as $MWT = ([2 \times MT] / ED) \times 100\%$. Pulmonary arteries sized $25 \mu\text{m} < ED < 100 \mu\text{m}$ were included in the analysis. For each animal, 18-43 pulmonary arteries were measured in two orthogonal directions using Fiji image analysis software. The variation in the number of analyzed pulmonary arteries/mouse is due to sectioning artifacts that affect how many cross-sectioned arteries were suitable for the analysis of MWT. Each MWT data point represents the average of all analyzed pulmonary arteries from a single animal.

For analysis of CD11b⁺ and CD4⁺ cells per pulmonary artery, images of pulmonary arteries were randomly acquired from transversal sections stained for CD11b and CD4 immunohistochemistry at 10× and 40× magnification. Images were acquired using an inverted automated EVOS M7000 microscope (ThermoFisher). The microscopy images for MDA5^{-/-} and MDA5^{+/+} mice were acquired simultaneously under the same conditions. The number of CD11b⁺ and CD4⁺ cells was counted using Fiji in a blinded manner. Each CD11b and CD4 data point represents the average of all analyzed pulmonary arteries of one animal.

Protein Isolation and Immunoblotting

Protein isolation and Western blotting were performed as published previously (2, 3). Following lysis with RIPA buffer with proteinase and phosphatase inhibitors, 10-20 μg protein (cell lysate) and 40 μg protein (whole lung lysate) were resolved by SDS-PAGE at 90 V for 60-80 min. Then, the protein was blotted at 270 mA for 2 hours onto a

nitrocellulose membrane for antibody staining and chemiluminescence detection (ECL). Membranes were blocked with 5% bovine serum albumin/0.5% Tween20/TBS for 1 hour. Primary antibody incubation was performed in 5% bovine serum albumin/0.5% Tween20/TBS overnight at 4 °C, followed by secondary antibody incubation in 5% bovine serum albumin/0.5% Tween20/TBS for 1h (horse radish peroxidase-conjugated secondary antibodies). Images were obtained by developing an ECL solution and image acquisition with a Biorad ChemiDoc gel imager with ImageLab software (Biorad, Hercules, CA). Densitometry with automated background subtraction was performed with ImageLab (Biorad, Hercules, CA).

Lung tissue interferon levels

Interferons in mouse lung tissue were assayed via multiplex ELISA (Meso Scale Discovery, Rockville, MD) according to the manufacturer's protocol.

RNA isolation

RNA isolation was performed as published previously (3-5). RNA was isolated using the Qiagen miRNeasy mini kit (217084) or the Qiagen RNeasy plus kit (74134) according to the manufacturer's instructions, followed by DNase digestion (miRNeasy kit) to remove potential genomic DNA contamination. DNase I treatment was performed at 0.1 U/μl final activity for 15 min at room temperature, followed by the addition of 25 mM EDTA and incubation at 65°C for 10 min to inactivate DNase. Total mRNA concentrations were measured using Nanodrop (ThermoFisher Scientific).

qRT-PCR

A master mix was prepared containing 10x RT buffer, dNTP mix, RT random primers, and RNase-free water for the reverse transcriptase (RT) reaction. This mix was added to the RNA samples, and the reaction was run in a Thermocycler (T100, Bio-Rad) under the following conditions: 10 minutes at 25°C, 120 minutes at 37°C, and 5 minutes at 85°C. Following reverse transcription, cDNA samples were diluted 1:10 in nuclease-free water for real-time PCR. For each well in a 384-well plate, a master mix was prepared containing 1 μ L of forward and reverse primer mix, 5 μ L of SYBR Green master mix (iTaq, 1725120, Bio-Rad), and 4 μ L of diluted cDNA. Quantitative real-time (qRT)-PCR was performed using the CFX384 Touch Real-Time PCR system (Bio-Rad) with the following cycle conditions: initial denaturation at 95°C for 30 seconds, followed by 45 cycles of 95°C for 5 seconds and 60°C for 30 seconds. A melt curve analysis was then performed by increasing the temperature from 65°C to 95°C in 0.5°C increments every 5 seconds. The primers sequences are listed in Tables S1 and S3.

Bulk RNA-sequencing

RNA sequencing was performed by Novogene (Sacramento, CA). mRNA was purified from total RNA using poly-T oligo-attached magnetic beads. After fragmentation, the first strand cDNA was synthesized using random hexamer primers, followed by the second strand cDNA synthesis. The library was ready after end repair, A-tailing, adapter ligation, size selection, amplification, and purification. The library was checked with Qubit and real-time PCR for quantification and bioanalyzer for size distribution detection.

Quantified libraries were pooled and sequenced on Illumina platforms according to the effective library concentration and the amount of data.

Raw Data was analyzed using ROSALIND (<https://rosalind.bio/>) as published previously (3) (ROSALIND, Inc., San Diego, CA). In brief, reads were trimmed using cutadapt (6). Quality scores were assessed using FastQC (7). Reads were aligned to the Homo sapiens genome build GRCh38 using STAR (8). Individual sample reads were quantified using Htseq (9) and normalized via Relative Log Expression (RLE) using DESeq2 R library (10). Read Distribution percentages, violin plots, identity heatmaps, and sample MDS plots were generated as part of the QC step using RseQC (11). Deseq2 was also used to calculate fold changes and p-values and perform optional covariate correction. Hypergeometric distribution was used to analyze the enrichment of pathways, gene ontology, domain structure, and other ontologies. The topGO R library (12) was used to determine local similarities and dependencies between GO terms in order to perform Elim pruning correction. Several database sources were referenced for enrichment analysis, including Interpro (13), NCBI (14), MsigDB (15, 16), REACTOME (17), and WikiPathways (18). Enrichment was calculated relative to a set of background genes relevant for the experiment. Following the identification of differentially expressed genes with fold changes of >1.5 and an adjusted P value of <0.05 , downstream analysis of functions and pathway enrichment was performed using Ingenuity Pathway analysis (Qiagen). The volcano plot was generated with Rosalind, and a summary of cell functions and pathways was assembled in GraphPad Prism 10.0. The raw RNA-seq data are available from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) repository with accession number GSE314466.

Single-cell RNA sequencing analysis

Publicly available single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) data from human pulmonary artery tissue were obtained from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GSE210248). The dataset comprised samples from healthy donors (n=3, controls) and patients with pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH, n=3). Raw count matrices were reprocessed using the Seurat package (v4.x) in R (19). Cells with fewer than 200 detected genes and genes detected in fewer than 3 cells were excluded. Data were normalized using the LogNormalize method with a scale factor of 10,000, and the top 2,000 highly variable genes were identified using variance stabilizing transformation.

To correct for sample-level batch effects while preserving biological variation between disease conditions, Harmony batch correction (20) was applied to the principal component analysis (PCA) embeddings using sample identity as the batch variable. Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) dimensionality reduction was performed on the first 30 Harmony-corrected dimensions. Cell type annotations from the original study were retained for downstream analyses. The analyzed populations included endothelial cells (Endo 1, Endo 2), smooth muscle cells (SMC 1, SMC 2), fibroblasts, monocytes/macrophages, T cells, NK cells, B cells, dendritic cells, granulocytes, mast cells, and epithelial cells.

IFIH1 expression was compared between Donor and PAH conditions within each cell type using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. Log₂ fold change was calculated as $\log_2(\text{mean}_{\text{PAH}}/\text{mean}_{\text{Donor}})$. P-values were adjusted for multiple comparisons using the Benjamini-Hochberg method. A panel of innate immune sensor and interferon signaling

genes (DDX58, TLR3, TLR4, TLR7, TLR8, TLR9, MAVS, IRF3, IRF7, STAT1, STAT2, OAS1, OAS2, ISG15, MX1) was analyzed alongside IFIH1.

Antibody validation

The antibodies used in this study were validated for specificity by the vendors, previous work from other laboratories, and our current study. **MDA5** (LS-A10978, LS Bio) was validated by LifeSpan Biologicals for use in immunohistochemistry using the PathPlus Validation Process by a combination of antibody specificity, tissue validation, immunohistochemistry validation, and pathology analysis. In addition, we validated this antibody by comparing staining with scRNA-seq data. **MDA5** (5321, Cell Signaling Technology) was validated using siRNA knockdown in human cells (main manuscript Figure 3A) and in mouse lung tissue using MDA5 whole body knockout mice (main manuscript Figure 2A). **α -SMA** (M0851, Agilent DAKO) was validated by Boulday et al. via loss of smooth muscle actin-specific signal in the dorsal aorta of embryos (21). **β -actin** (A5441, Millipore Sigma, Burlington, MA) was validated by the manufacturer by a combination of immunocytochemistry and immunoblotting. **CD11b** (NB110-89474, Novus Biologicals, Centennial, CO) was validated using dual RNA-scope ISH-IHC by the manufacturer. **CD4** (ab125711, Abcam) was validated by the manufacturer by overexpression of CD4.

TABLES

Primer	Sequence
<i>Cxcl10</i> forward	5'-GACTCAAGGGATCCCTCTC-3'
<i>Cxcl10</i> reverse	5'-ATGGCCCTCATTCTCACTG-3'
<i>Cxcl2</i> forward	5'-TCAATGCCTGAAGACCCTG-3'
<i>Cxcl2</i> reverse	5'-AGAGTGGCTATGACTTCTGTC-3'
<i>Ifitm3</i> forward	5'-CCGTGAAGTCTAGGGATCG-3'
<i>Ifitm3</i> reverse	5'-CAAGGTGCTGATGTTTCAGG-3'
<i>Il1b</i> forward	5'-CCTCAAAGGAAAGAATCTATACCTG-3'
<i>Il1b</i> reverse	5'-CTTGGGATCCACACTCTCC-3'
<i>Il6</i> forward	5'-TACCACTTCACAAGTCGGA-3'
<i>Il6</i> reverse	5'-AATTGCCATTGCACAACCTC-3'
<i>Mx1</i> forward	5'-TGCTGTACTGCTAAGTCCA-3'
<i>Mx1</i> reverse	5'-GAAGTGAAGTCGGATCAGG-3'
<i>Tnfa</i> forward	5'-TTCTCATTCTGCTTGTGG-3'
<i>Tnfa</i> reverse	5'-TTGGGAACTTCTCATCCCT-3'

Table S1. Mouse primers

Parameter	Value (mean \pm SD)
RVSP (mmHg)	16.66 \pm 2.03
Heartrate (bmp) (catheterization)	294 \pm 84.57
Fulton index (%)	18.48 \pm 4.84
Bodyweight (g)	25.87 \pm 2.99
TAPSE (mm)	0.81 \pm 0.13
PAAT/PET	0.49 \pm 0.13
RV cardiac output (mL/min)	13.59 \pm 6.21
Heartrate (bmp) (echocardiography)	492 \pm 72.51

Table S2. Baseline characteristics of untreated (normoxic) MDA5^{-/-} mice. n=4

(RVSP and heartrate, n=2 female and n=2 male mice), n=6 for all other parameters

(n=3 female and n=3 male mice). RVSP: right ventricular systolic pressure; TAPSE: tricuspid annular plane systolic excursion (echocardiography); PAAT/PET: pulmonary artery acceleration time vs. pulmonary ejection time (echocardiography);

Primer	Sequence
<i>B2M</i> forward	5'-GCTCGCGCTACTCTCTCTTT-3'
<i>B2M</i> reverse	5'-CCCCACCTCTAAGTTGCCAG-3'
<i>IFIH1</i> forward (FH1_IFIH1)	5'-GATTAACTCCTCATACCCAC-3'
<i>IFIH1</i> reverse (BH1_IFIH1)	5'-GTCTGACAATTGAACACCAG-3'
<i>IFITM3</i> forward	5'-TCTGGTCCCTGTTCAACAC-3'
<i>IFITM3</i> reverse	5'-GTCCCTAGACTTCACGGAG-3'
<i>IFNB1</i> forward	5'-ATTCTAACTGCAACCTTTCG-3'
<i>IFNB1</i> reverse	5'-GTTGTAGCTCATGGAAAGAG-3'
<i>MAVS1</i> forward	5'-CAGCAGAAATGAGGAGACC-3'
<i>MAVS1</i> reverse	5'-CTATTCTCAGAGCTGCTGTC-3'
<i>MKI67</i> forward	5'-ATACGTGAACAGGAGCCAG-3'
<i>MKI67</i> reverse	5'-CCTTGGAATCTTGAGCTTTCTC-3'
<i>MX1</i> forward	5'-GGGCTTTGGAATTCTGTGG-3'
<i>MX1</i> reverse	5'-ATTCAGGGAGTGGGAGTC-3'
<i>OAS1</i> forward	5'-CTGGCTGAATTACCCATGC-3'
<i>OAS1</i> reverse	5'-CTGAGCCTTTGTCTCATCAG-3'
<i>PCNA</i> forward	5'-AGTGGAGAACTTGGAAATGG-3'
<i>PCNA</i> reverse	5'-CTCTATGGTAACAGCTTCCTC-3'
<i>TBP</i> forward	5'-GCCAAGAGTGAAGAACAG-3'
<i>TBP</i> reverse	5'-GAAGTCCAAGAACTTAGCTG-3'

Table S3. Human primers

Condition	Age	Gender
Control 1	27	male
Control 2	37	female
Control 3	57	female
IPAH 1	15	male
IPAH 2	49	female
IPAH 3	61	male

Table S4: Patient demographics for the human lung tissue samples in Figure 1A.

Condition	Age	Gender
Control 1	57	Female
Control 2	53	Female
Control 3	25	Male
Control 4	47	Male
Control 5	49	Female
Control 6	55	Female
Control 7	13	Male
Control 8	51	Female
PAH 1	16	Male
PAH 2	27	Female
PAH 3	44	Male
PAH 4	16	Female
PAH 5	31	Male

Table S5: Patient demographics for the primary human pulmonary artery endothelial cells in Figure 1B.

Condition	Age	Gender
Control 1	32	Female
Control 2	33	Female
Control 3	37	Male
Control 4	40	Male
PAH 1	53	Female
PAH 2	36	Female
PAH 3	31	Male
PAH 4	45	Male

Table S6: Patient demographics for the primary human pulmonary artery smooth muscle cells in Figure 1C.

Age	Gender
55	Female
49	Male
49	Female
35	Male
51	Female
49	Male
51	Female

Table S7: Patient demographics for the control primary human pulmonary artery endothelial cells used for in vitro experiments in Figure 3 and Supplemental Figure S4.

Age	Gender
41	female
44	female
51	male

Table S8: Patient demographics for the control primary human pulmonary artery smooth muscle cells used for in vitro experiments in Supplemental Figure S5.

Cell Type	n_Donor	n_PAH	mean_Donor	mean_PAH	log ₂ FC	P value	Adj. P val
Mono / Macs	1538	2087	0.035	0.061	0.823	0.000000408	0.00000571
DC	233	350	0.024	0.048	1.016	0.033	0.229
NK cells	412	646	0.017	0.042	1.311	0.061	0.285
SMC 2	303	606	0.018	0.028	0.625	0.135	0.377
T cells	283	3023	0.011	0.032	1.563	0.123	0.377
Endo 1	863	244	0.090	0.060	-0.577	0.227	0.413
Mast cells	83	230	0.043	0.016	-1.417	0.191	0.413
Epithelial	387	77	0.016	0.000	N/A	0.236	0.413
Granulocytes	979	251	0.029	0.045	0.656	0.303	0.425
Endo 2	444	202	0.067	0.042	-0.661	0.285	0.425
SMC 1	1576	641	0.011	0.015	0.423	0.433	0.552
T / NK cells	163	1929	0.030	0.037	0.299	0.799	0.861
Fibro	4326	197	0.022	0.021	-0.051	0.760	0.861
B cells	169	462	0.042	0.040	-0.082	0.876	0.876

Table S9: *IFIH1* (MDA5) gene statistical comparison between cell types from GSE210248. Statistical comparison results, including sample sizes, mean expression, log₂ fold change (FC), P values, and adjusted P values for each cell type. Mono / Macs: Monocytes / Macrophages; DC: dendritic cells; NK cells: natural killer cells; SMC: smooth muscle cell; Endo: endothelial cells; Fibro: fibroblasts.

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES:

Supplemental Figure S1. (A-B) Heart rate (A, during invasive right heart catheterization and B, during echocardiography) and (C) body weight of MDA5^{+/+} and MDA5^{-/-} mice exposed to chronic hypoxia/SU5416 for 21 days. Red symbols indicate female mice, open symbols indicate male mice. The difference in heart rate between (A) and (B) is due to different types of anesthesia.

Supplemental Figure S2. mRNA levels of *Tnfa* and *Il1b* in the lung tissue of MDA5^{+/+} and MDA5^{-/-} mice exposed to chronic hypoxia/SU5416 for 21 days. Red symbols indicate female mice, open symbols indicate male mice.

Supplemental Figure S3. Interferon- β (IFN- β) levels in protein lysate from lung tissue of MDA5^{+/+} and MDA5^{-/-} mice exposed to chronic hypoxia/SU5416 for 21 days. Red symbols indicate female mice, open symbols indicate male mice. Note that the levels are in general at the lower detection limit of the assay.

Supplemental Figure S4. Gap closure and transendothelial electric resistance in PAECs following control and MDA5 siRNA. (A) Representative images (0h and 18h) and quantification show that MDA5 gene silencing reduces gap closure in PAECs in vitro. (scale bar 500 μm) $n=6$ replicates per group. These data are representative of three independent replicate experiments. (B) Transendothelial electric resistance (TEER, barrier function) is reduced in MDA5 siRNA PAECs. $n=6$ replicates per group. Data presented as mean \pm SD. Data was analyzed by t-test. The numbers in the graphs indicate the P values.

Supplemental Figure S5. mRNA expression of proliferation markers PCNA and MKI67 following MDA5 (IFIH1) knockdown in 3 primary human PASM lines (2 female, 1 male) and an immortalized human PASM line. Each data point represents the average of all technical replicates for one biological replicate (independent experiment). Data is displayed as single points and the mean \pm SD. Data was analyzed by the Mann-Whitney test. The numbers in the graphs indicate the P values.

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